

Improvements in the Characteristics of Plant Fiber Reinforced Concrete

Md Rakibul Islam

Civil Engineering, Sichuan University, China

Md Rafat Ul Isalm

Civil Engineering, College of Architecture and Environment, Sichuan University, China

Muhammad Rashid

Civil Engineering, College of Architecture and Environment, Sichuan University, China

Faisal Ahammad

Civil engineering and architecture, China Three Gorges University, China

Monjurul Islam

Civil Engineering, Changsha University of Science and Technology, China

Suggested Citation

Islam, M.R., Isalm, M.R.U., Rashid, M., Ahammad, F., & Islam, M. (2024). Improvements in the Characteristics of Plant Fiber Reinforced Concrete. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 552-568.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).53](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).53)

Abstract:

Plant Fiber is lightweight, has a high specific strength, and the ultimate elongation is high and can improve the shortcoming of concrete. Concrete is easy to crack and break, and its tensile strength and other mechanical properties are not high. The chemical composition and mechanical properties of some plant Fibers that are often used are analyzed first. The modification of plant Fiber will also be discussed. Firstly, the chemical composition and mechanical properties of some plant Fibers are analyzed, and the modification methods of plant Fibers are also discussed; then, the mechanical properties of plant Fiber-reinforced concrete, hydration properties,

heat preservation properties, durability, and other properties of plant Fiber-reinforced concrete are analyzed and summarized in detail. The conclusions are as follows. When the strength of concrete is increased by plant Fiber, the long Fiber is the best tensile strength method, the short Fiber is the most practical, and the length and content of the Fiber. The influence of factors such as water-cement ratio; plant Fiber can delay the release of the heat of hydration of cement by changing the hydration characteristics of cement, thereby improving the anti-cracking ability of mass concrete; concrete plant Fiber can improve the thermal stability and durability, and the lyotropic effect of plant Fiber on concrete Affect the flowability of paste. Plant Fibers can improve the thermal insulation and durability of concrete and reduce the thermal cracking of concrete. The plant Fiber is used as a reinforcement in the concrete of the railway foundation, which can enhance its tensile strength, impact strength, and flexural strength. The optimal loading range is 0.6-0.9%, and the long Fiber lay-flat method is the best. In the mixed method, these five physical reverse effects can be prepared in the range of 1.2-2.0%. The single tensile squeezing capacity of 30 plants using the mixed method is up to 3.69 MPa, which is the only chemical evaluation capacity of 46.5%.

Keywords: *Plant Fiber, Concrete, Mechanical Properties, Hydration Characteristics, Insulation Properties.*

Introduction

Concrete is currently the largest amount of building materials, but the low tensile strength of concrete, poor toughness, ease of cracking, and many other shortcomings have not yet been well resolved, which not only affects the scope of use and service life of concrete but also often lead to several major safety accidents. In recent years, people have begun to study concrete by adding various types of artificial Fibers to improve its mechanical properties, improve its safety, and achieve good results. For example, steel Fibers are mixed into concrete to make unreinforced ultra-high-performance concrete (ultra-high-performance concrete, UHPC) rectangular beam specimens, when loaded, the specimens show obvious ductile damage characteristics, and their ultimate torque can be increased by more than 100% (Gong, et al., 2023); carbon Fibers can be mixed into concrete to significantly improve the mechanical properties of mixed concrete, and often cause some major safety accidents. Concrete tensile and compressive strength, of which the tensile strength can reach 150% of ordinary concrete, modulus of elasticity and ductility have also been improved (Yin, et al., 2023); basalt Fiber, polyvinyl alcohol Fibers, etc. into the concrete have shown excellent enhancement effect (Jia, & Li, 2023; Zhang, 2023; Yang, et al., 2023; Niu, et al., 2023).

Though all kinds of man-made Fibers have a great effect on enhancing the mechanical properties of concrete, the production cost is high, and the process of production gives rise to carbon emissions. Based on the above situation, natural plant Fibers have gradually attracted the attention of researchers as a nutrient-rich and low-cost source. China is a large agricultural production country and nearly 1 billion tons of straw are produced every year. However, straw is low in density and inconvenient to transport, resulting in about 200 million tons of straw being discarded every year; this not only waste resource but also form new burden to the environment (Feng, et al., 2022). The use of plant Fibers instead of synthetic fibers to enhance the performance of concrete can solve

environmental problems, and at the same time can greatly reduce the cost of the project.

Plant Fiber is a renewable natural Fiber, with a wide range of sources, low price, low carbon and environmental protection, specific strength, and other advantages (Li, et al., 2020; Chen, et al., 2018; Li, Tabil, & Panigrahi, 2007). A large number of studies (Madhwani, Sathyan, & Mini, 2021; Talavera-Pech, et al., 2021; Guo, et al., 2022) show that concrete mixed with the appropriate amount of plant Fibers, not only can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete, reduce the manufacturing cost of concrete, but also improve the thermal insulation properties and durability of concrete. In this paper, for the characteristics of various types of plant Fibers, to explore the plant Fiber mechanical properties of concrete, hydration characteristics, thermal insulation, and other properties of the enhancement of the method and effect, and plant Fibers in the field of reinforcing the development of concrete in the outlook.

Research on Chemical Composition, Mechanical Properties, and Fiber Modification of Commonly Used Plant Fibers

Chemical Composition and Mechanical Properties of Common Plant Fibers

In simple terms, plant Fiber is mainly composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, or other components. Because the specific type of Fiber, growth conditions, plant growth years, plant growth location, extraction, processing methods, and other factors are different, the actual content of the above components is different. The difference will have a great impact on the mechanical properties of plant Fiber, generally, as long as the cellulose content of the plant Fiber is different, the mechanical properties of the plant Fiber, especially its strength and elastic modulus, are also different. The tensile and elastic moduli of different plant Fibers are logically very different. The mechanical properties and main chemical composition of

common plant Fibers are shown in Table 1 (Appendix) (Yan, Kasal, & Huang, 2016; Onuaguluchi, & Banthia, 2016; Wen, et al., 2022).

From Table 1, it can be seen that: Firstly, the tensile strength of flax, ramie, sisal, and other fibers is equal to or even higher than that of steel. When it is used to reinforce concrete materials, it can significantly improve the tensile and compressive capacity of concrete materials. The present strength of the material cannot be determined, and the ultimate cracking strength cannot be determined. Secondly, most plant Fibers have lower elastic modulus, only flax, ramie and other plant Fibers have a slightly higher modulus of elasticity than concrete, and the elastic modulus of pineapple Fiber and coconut Fiber is much lower than the elastic modulus of concrete, so plant Fibers are added. The effect of improving the initial cracking strength when mixed with concrete materials is not obvious. Third, the elongation at break of plant Fibers is much larger than that of concrete, but the elongation at break of coconut Fiber is much larger than that of other plant Fibers, it is generally elongated 3.5 to 23.5 times other fibers, up to 89.3 times (Munawar, Umemura, K., & Kawai, 2007; Jiang, et al., 2020), and it is very beneficial to the improvement of the high brittleness of concrete.

Modification of Plant Fibers

The microstructure of natural plant fibers is shown in Fig. 1 (Wei, & Meyer, 2015), where cellulose is a linear polymer composed of glucose with high tensile strength. Cellulose peripheral winding hemicellulose, cellulose filled with lignin, and other substances. Although the strength of lignin is very low, it as the cellulose support material, can make the cellulose in the best state of force. This unique cell structure of plant fiber gives it excellent mechanical properties; therefore, plant fiber-reinforced cementitious composites have the advantages of high strength, lightweight, and ductile damage (De Klerk, et al., 2020). However, due to the alkaline substance $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})$ produced by cement hydration, the inner part of concrete is weakly alkaline, and the lignin and hemicellulose in plant fibers are prone to their degradation in this alkaline environment, so the cellulose loses its support and fails to play its tensile role, which affects the durability of the structure (Filho, Silva, & Filho, 2013). At the same time, the hydrolysis products of lignin and hemicellulose also have a certain hindering effect on the hydration of cement (Bonnet-Masimbert, et al., 2020), affecting the normal growth of the strength of the concrete material, therefore, it is necessary to modify the plant fibers to improve the alkali corrosion resistance of plant fibers.

Figure 1. Microstructure of Natural Plants Fiber

Source: Wei, & Meyer, 2015)

The modification of plant fiber is to change the surface morphology of the fiber through physical or chemical methods, and at the same time to improve the ability of plant fiber to resist

alkaline substances. There are many ways to modify plant Fibers, commonly used are keratinization, alkali treatment, heat treatment, plasma treatment, and so on. The plant Fiber

for several wet and dry cycles can make the Fiber cell keratinization, not only improve its resistance to alkali corrosion but also improve the tensile strength of the Fiber, fiber cell keratinization also helps to reduce the changes in the volume of the Fiber, thereby enhancing the adhesion between the Fiber and the substrate (Bonnet-Masimbert, et al., 2020; Ferreira, et al., 2017; Ferreira, et al., 2015; Claramunt, et al., 2011); Alkali treatment is to use a certain concentration of NaOH aqueous solution on the plant Fiber for immersion after the alkali treatment can be removed from the Fibers. Alkali treatment uses a certain concentration of NaOH solution to soak the plant Fiber, alkali treatment can remove part of the Fiber hemicellulose, lignin, pectin, wax, and other components, improve the Fiber matrix bond, improve Fiber strength and stability, at the same time, make the Fiber thinner and the surface becomes rougher, to enhance the adhesion between the Fiber and the cement matrix (Liu, et al., 2009; Dos Santos, et al., 2022); heat treatment is the use of hemicellulose and lignin decomposition temperature is lower than the characteristics of the cellulose, in the temperature of 200 °C under the cooking or immersion, hemicellulose and lignin partially decomposed, thereby enhancing the fiber and the matrix of bonding. Partial decomposition of hemicellulose and lignin, thus improving the stability of the fiber, at the same time, is also conducive to reducing the hydrolysis products of cement hydration retardation (Sawsen, et al., 2015; Sellami, Merzoud, & Amziane, 2013; Farooqi, & Ali, 2019); plasma treatment can be purified on the surface of plant Fibers, roughened to improve the stability of the plant Fibers and improve the adhesion of Fibers with the cement matrix materials (Lee, et al., 2003; Sun, 2016; Barra, et al., 2015).

Mechanical Properties of Plant Fiber Reinforced Concrete

Tensile Strength

The tensile strength of ordinary concrete is relatively low, about one-tenth of its

compressive strength, and it shows great brittleness when damaged. Ordinary concrete mixed with plant fibers, not only can improve the tensile strength of concrete but also can improve the elongation at the break of concrete so that the brittle damage characteristics of concrete to plastic damage characteristics. De Andrade Silva et al. (2009) have prepared a cementitious composite reinforced laminate that uses sisal long Fiber, which is generally laid in five layers, and has a Fiber content of 10%. The size of the laminate is 400 mm × 50 mm × 12 mm. The result of the tensile test on the laminate shows that the modulus of elasticity of the laminate to crack is 34.17 GPa; the laminate to be destroyed, the average ultimate tensile strength is 12 MPa, and the average ultimate tensile strain is 1.53, the performance of this sisal Fiber cement board has been significantly improved in addition to the tensile elastic modulus and the tensile strength of the ultimate tensile strain is significantly improved, and more suitable for engineering utilization. Shang, et al., (2019) selected bamboo Fiber, hemp Fiber, sisal Fiber, ramie Fiber, and four plant Fibers. The volume fraction was 2%, and the doped cementitious material was made from the fiber using two two-tier mixing short Fiber and long fiber. The glued piece is then of a dumbbell shape. The uniaxial tensile test was carried out on the dumbbell specimens. Table 2 shows the characteristic parameters of the stress-strain curves of uniaxial tensile test specimens with long-fiber layered plain specimens (where the letter T after the specimen type stands for long-fiber layered plain, the number before the parentheses stand for the mean value, and the number inside the parentheses stands for the standard deviation).

From the data in Table 2, it can be seen that after the uniaxial tensile cracking of the four specimens, all of them showed higher subsequent load carrying capacity, i.e., showed obvious strain hardening characteristics, and the ultimate tensile strains all reached more than 2%. Among them, the ultimate tensile strength of the sisal fiber layered specimen was over 2%. 4.081 MPa, which is 53% higher than the initial cracking strength of 2.666 MPa, shows good and

stable strain hardening and multi-seam cracking characteristics.

In addition to the use of long fibers laying method to enhance the tensile strength of concrete, scholars have also studied the method of fiber mixing to enhance the tensile strength of concrete, because the enhancement of the tensile strength of short fibers mixing concrete is affected by some factors, there is a situation where different results from different researchers. Azzmi et al. Find that, for the cementitious composites reinforced with red hemp fiber with lengths of 25 mm and 50 mm, the tensile strength of the short-fiber reinforced matrix increased by 25.8%, and the long fibers only increased by 6.12%.

Much lower than the reinforcing effect of short fibers, and the optimal fiber content of short fibers and long fibers are about 0.75% and 0.50%, respectively, suggesting that the short fibers can be blended into a greater amount to improve the reinforcing effect. On the contrary, Lam et al. (2015) concluded that the use of a 50 mm length of red hemp fibers has a better reinforcing effect than a 25 mm length of red hemp fibers. The main reason for the inconsistency between the two results may be due to the difference in the amount of water used in mixing the concrete. Azzmi et al. used a lower water-cement ratio, which resulted in the long red hemp fibers not being evenly distributed, thus decreasing the strength of the mix (Azzmi, & Yatim, 2018).

Table 2. Characteristic Parameters of Uniaxial Tensile Stress-Strain Curves

Type of specimen	First cracking strength / MPa	Ultimate strength / MPa	Ultimate tensile strain / %
Bamboo-T	2.407 (0.131)	2.646 (0.185)	2.112 (0.376)
Hemp-T	1.294 (0.113)	1.599 (0.129)	2.449 (0.863)
Sisal-T	2.666 (0.516)	4.081 (0.164)	2.048 (0.168)
Ramie-T	3.667 (0.321)	5.377 (0.001)	3.263 (0.074)

From the research results of different scholars, the use of the long fiber paving method to enhance the tensile strength of concrete, tensile strength increase, and stability are significantly better than the method of short fiber doping, the main reason is: first of all, the use of long fiber paving, the researchers are long fibers parallel to the direction of the force, which ensures that all the fibers can withstand the tensile force, to maximize the increase in the tensile strength of the composite, while when the use of short fibers, the fiber random distribution, some fibers and the direction of the tension to form a certain angle, can only partially bear the tension, and some fibers and even fibers cannot even partially bear the tension. Tensile strength, and when using short fibers in the mixing method, the fiber random distribution, some fibers and the direction of tension to form a certain angle, can only partially bear the tensile force, there are fibers and even perpendicular to the direction of tension, cannot bear the tensile force, which affects the fiber on the tensile strength of the

concrete enhancement; Secondly, when using long fibers laid flat, the fiber's long diameter is relatively large, the fiber is not easy to be pulled out, so that the full use of the tensile strength of the fiber, and thus can Secondly, when using long fiber paving, the fiber diameter is relatively large, the fiber is not easy to be pulled out, so it can make full use of the tensile strength of the fiber, and when using short fiber doping, the fiber diameter is relatively small, when the composite material is tensile cracking, there will be a part of the fiber at the crack is pulled out, so that the fiber's strength can't give full play to the fiber's tensile strength enhancement effect on the concrete. Although the long fiber laying method to enhance the tensile strength of concrete is more effective, in the actual engineering applications, some of the structure of the force will change with the change of conditions, and the direction of the tension is not determined, in this case, can only be used to enhance the tensile strength of concrete using short fibers within the mixing method, so that

the short fiber mixing method has a wider range of applications.

Compressive Strength

The process of concrete damage under pressure is the process of crack generation, expansion, and final destruction, in addition to improving the compressive strength of concrete by increasing the strength of cement paste, people also study the fiber reinforced concrete to delay the crack generation and expansion, to improve the compressive strength of concrete. Zhou et

al. (2020) conducted a pressure test on kenaf fiber reinforced cement-based material (KFRC), and the load-deflection curve is shown in Fig. 2 (where NC denotes the unadulterated fiber specimen, KFRC denotes the kenaf fiber reinforced specimen, and A, B, C denote the three strength grades, number 1, 2, 3 denote the three strength grades, and A, B, C denote the three strength grades. A, B, and C, respectively, three strength levels, serial numbers 1, 2, and 3, respectively, the volume of fiber doping for 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%).

Figure 2. Load-Deformation Curves of Compressive Specimens

Source: Zhou et al. (2020)

As can be seen from Fig. 2, the compression specimens with different water-cement ratios (different strength classes) show similar patterns. The curves of the unadulterated fiber-reinforced specimen (NC) and the red hemp fiber-reinforced specimen (KFRC) showed obvious separation after reaching the maximum load, and the decreasing section of the curve of NC was very steep, which showed the brittle damage characteristics, while the decreasing section of the KFRC was relatively gentle, and the larger the fiber mixing, the flatter the decreasing section of the curve was, which indicated that the fiber had a significant influence on the compression of the specimens.

The more pronounced increase in the ductility of the specimen, this phenomenon also reflects the plant fiber in the specimen after cracking the subsequent tensile bearing capacity of the

specimen to improve the ductility of the specimen plays an important role. From the peak comparison of the curves in Figure 2 can also be clearly seen, after the doping of red hemp fiber, the compressive strength of the specimen decreased significantly, and the greater the amount of doping, the greater the reduction in compressive strength.

The reasons for the decrease in compressive strength of specimen may have the following two points: firstly, the tubular structure of plant fiber leads to the compression modulus of fiber is much lower than that of cementitious material, therefore, after doping the plant fiber, the fiber occupies the space of cementitious material, weakening the compression area of the cementitious material, while the fiber itself can't be synergistically pressurized with the matrix material, which results in the decrease of

compressive strength of composite materials; secondly, the doping of Secondly, after mixing plant fiber, due to the water-absorbing effect of plant fiber, it reduces the compatibility of cement slurry mixing, which reduces the compactness of composite materials, and the larger the amount of fiber mixing, the greater the impact on the compactness of composite materials, thus the greater the impact on the compressive strength of composite materials.

Zhang Guanzhi et al. (2019) After treatment with NaOH solution, *Artemisia annua* fibers were mixed into C20 concrete to make specimens with different contents, and a pressure test was carried out, and the test results are shown in Table 3. The test results are shown in Table 3. It can be seen from the table that the different fiber content has different effects on the compressive strength of the specimens, but all of them show the effect of improving the compressive strength.

Table 3. Cubic Compressive Strength of Concrete with Different Fiber Incorporation Rates

Amount of <i>artemisia flavescens</i> / (kg-m ⁻³)	0	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50
Average compressive strength of cube / MPa	24.65	26.28	26.46	26.23	25.22	25.29	25.50

Çomak, Bideci, & Salli Bideci, (2018), Naraganti, Pannem, & Putta, (2019), Gupta, & Kumar, (2019), Islam, & Ahmed, (2018), Liu, Liu, & Zhang, (2012) mixed a variety of plant fibers such as hemp fiber, sisal fiber, coconut palm fiber, jute fiber, rapeseed straw fiber, and other plant fibers into concrete to study its effect on the compressive strength of concrete, the results show that various fibers on the compressive strength of concrete have different degrees of improvement, in the study of Çomak et al. (2018), the increase of the compressive strength of the concrete of the hemp fiber reaches 30%.

There is a big difference between the research results of Zhang Guanzhi et al. (2019), Çomak, Bideci, & Salli Bideci, (2018), Naraganti, Pannem, & Putta, (2019), Gupta, & Kumar, (2019), Islam, & Ahmed, (2018), Liu, Liu, & Zhang, (2012) and Zhou et al. (2020), which may be attributed to the fact that the former used a larger water-cement ratio to improve the compatibility of the concrete mixture, thus reducing the adverse effect of fibers on the compactness of the material, and at the same time, a large number of transverse fibers played a restraining role on the transverse deformation of the specimen under compression, so that the cementitious material was in a three-way stress state, which indirectly improved the compressive strength of the specimen. At the same time, a large number of transverse fibers played a

restraining effect on the transverse deformation of the specimen under compression, so that the cementitious material was in a three-way stress state, which in turn indirectly enhanced the compressive strength of the specimen.

The results of different researchers, different researchers used different concrete water-cement ratios, different types of fibers, different fiber lengths, mixing amounts, production methods, and so on, which led to large differences in the experimental results. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth study on the optimal mixing ratio, fiber dosage, fiber length, and other factors of plant fiber-reinforced concrete composites according to the stress characteristics of the materials under different working conditions, to improve the reinforcing effect of plant fibers on the compressive strength of concrete.

Impact Resistance

The elongation at break of plant fibers is usually 5~10 times that of ordinary plain concrete, and it has a good energy absorption effect, so the incorporation of plant fibers in concrete can effectively improve the impact resistance of concrete. The study shows that: the treated multi-bundle filamentous straw fibers added, the impact strength of lightweight aggregate concrete is significantly increased, and the concrete's fracture resistance has also been

improved (Zhang, et al., 2019; Li, et al., 2013) palm leaf fibers mixed into high-strength concrete, its toughness and impact resistance have increased, and palm leaf fibers show similar properties with glass fibers (Al-Oraimi, & Seibi, 1995); bamboo pulp fibers added to cement mortar when the mass fraction reaches 16%, its fracture toughness can be increased to 16%, and its fracture toughness can be improved by the addition of bamboo pulp fibers to cement mortar. When bamboo pulp fiber is added into cement mortar, when the mass fraction reaches 16%, its fracture toughness can be 32 times higher than that of cement mortar (Xie, 2016).

In cement mortar mixed with 4% by volume of coconut fiber, its toughness can be increased by 302%, and effectively improve its impact resistance (Hwang, et al., 2016). The use of sisal fiber reinforcement of high-strength coral aggregate seawater concrete can increase its energy absorption capacity by 49.06% ~ 140.29% compared with the plain concrete, thus improving its impact resistance (Ma, et al., 2020). Table 4 shows the results of the impact test of mortar boards made of cement mortar by incorporating coir Fibers of length 40 (Ramakrishna, & Sundararajan, 2005).

Table 4. Impact Energy Absorbed by Slab Specimens

Fiber content / %	0	0.50	1.00	1.50	2.00
Impact absorbed energy / J	13.98	67.10	73.63	164.03	253.50

As can be seen from Table 4, with the increase of plant Fiber dosage, the ability of the mortar slab to absorb energy under impact load increases rapidly, and the impact resistance also rises rapidly. Therefore, plant Fiber can effectively enhance the impact resistance of concrete.

Plant Fiber Enhanced Crack Resistance of Mass Concrete

In the construction of dams, piers, and other mass concrete structures, often due to the concentrated release of the heat of hydration of cement, resulting in a rapid increase in the internal temperature of the structure, the structure of the excessive temperature difference between the inside and outside of the structure is very easy to trigger the cracking of the concrete, therefore, the control of the release of the heat of hydration of the mass concrete construction is an important task. Plant fiber belongs to polysaccharides, which have a certain retardation effect on cement hydration, and can enhance the crack resistance of mass concrete by changing the release of hydration heat.

Ribeiro et al. (2020) made concrete specimens with different proportions of bagasse fibers and

installed electric thermocouples inside and on the surface of the specimens to measure the temperature of the concrete during the setting process, to study the release of heat of hydration during the hydration process of cement. Figure 3 shows the temperature change curves of different specimens and different parts of the specimens during the cement hydration process (in figure, C represents the control specimen; BF2 represents the specimen mixed with 2% by volume of bagasse fibers; BF5 represents the specimen mixed with 5% by volume of bagasse fibers; BA represents the specimen mixed with 2% by volume of bagasse fibers, and at the same time mixed with 5% by volume of bagasse ash; FA represents the specimen mixed with 2% by volume of bagasse fibers; and FA represents the specimen mixed with 5% by volume of bagasse ash; and FA represents the specimen mixed with 5% by volume of bagasse ash. FA means the specimen was mixed with 2% by volume of bagasse fiber and 5% by volume of bagasse ash; FA means the specimen was mixed with 2% by volume of bagasse fiber and 5% by volume of bagasse ash. (5% fly ash).

Figure 3. Temperature Change Curves of the Cement Hydration Process

Source: Ribeiro et al. (2020)

It can be seen from Fig. 3: Firstly, compared with the control specimen without bagasse fiber, the peak temperature of all the specimens with bagasse fiber was reduced, and the peak value was shifted significantly, among which the peak temperatures of the specimens BF2 and BF5 were reduced the most, with a drop of more than 4 °C, and the peak value was shifted by more than 4 h. The main reason for the reduction of the peak temperature and the shift in the peak value is that the sugar substances produced by fiber hydrolysis formed a protective layer on the surface of partially hydrated cement particles, which slowed down the penetration of water into the cement particles, thus delaying the hydration reaction process. The main reason for the decrease and shift of peak temperature is that the sugar substances produced by fiber hydrolysis form a protective layer on the surface of partially hydrated cement particles, which slows down the penetration of water into the cement particles, thus slowing down the hydration reaction process, and at the same time, the fiber hydrolysis process absorbs a part of the heat of hydration generated by the hydration reaction of the cement; Secondly, BF5 has a lower peak temperature and a shift of peak temperature than that of BF2, but there is not a big difference between the two, which is mainly because more sugar cane bagasse fibers are mixed into the BF5, and the peak temperature is shifted by more than 4 °C. The main reason is that after more bagasse fibers are mixed into BF5, although there are more sugars to reduce the heat of hydration, the increase of bagasse

fibers improves the heat preservation of concrete, which hinders the dissipation of the heat of hydration, so the peak temperature is not reduced much even though more bagasse is mixed into BF5 than into BF2. Finally, the number of fibers in the specimens BA, FA, and BF2 is the same, but the peak temperatures of specimens BA and FA are significantly higher than that of BF2, but the peak temperatures of specimens BF5 and BF2 are significantly higher than the peak temperature of specimens BF2. Finally, the three specimens of BA, FA, and BF2 had the same amount of fiber dosing, but the peak temperatures of specimens BA and FA were significantly higher than those of BF2, which was mainly due to the lower water-cement ratios of specimens BA and FA, and the fact that the bagasse ash and fly ash weakened the hydrolysis of cellulose, thus decreasing the retardation effect of fiber on the hydration reaction of cement.

Chakraborty et al. (2013) investigated the effect of natural jute fibers on the setting and hydration properties of cement using various analytical techniques such as thermal analysis, infrared spectroscopy, and X-ray diffraction, and the results showed that the hydration kinetics of cement slowed down as the content of jute fibers in the cement matrix increased. When the content of jute fibers in the cement was varied in the range of 0.5%~4.0% (mass fraction), the initial and final setting time of the cement were divided into two parts: (1) the initial and final setting time of the cement and (2) the final setting time of the cement.

The variations were 148~180 min and 191~246 min respectively, which indicated that jute fiber had a significant delaying effect on cement hydration.

Plant fibers as reinforcing materials can improve the crack resistance of concrete, at the same time, some of the hydrolysis products of plant fibers can also slow down the hydration rate of cement, reduce and delay the temperature peak in the process of setting and hardening of mass concrete, thus further enhancing the crack resistance of mass concrete.

Plant Fiber Enhanced Concrete Insulation

Thermal insulation performance refers to the insulation capacity of the material on the thermal energy, improve the thermal insulation performance of building materials to reduce the building energy consumption is of great significance, and the thermal conductivity of the material is directly related to the thermal insulation performance of the material, the lower the coefficient of thermal conductivity, the better the thermal insulation performance. The coefficient of thermal conductivity refers to the stable heat transfer conditions, 1 m thick material, the temperature difference between the two sides of the surface of 1 °C, 1 h through 1 cm³ area of heat transfer.

Figure 4. Effects of Fiber Content and Fiber Treatment Method on Thermal Conductivity of Concrete

The thermal conductivity of ordinary concrete is 1.3 ~ 2.3 W / (m·K), plant fibers have a special pore structure, in concrete or mortar mixed with plant fibers can produce countless disjointed pores inside the structure, preventing air flow, thus reducing the thermal conductivity of concrete materials, and, the smaller the diameter of the fiber, the larger the amount of mixing, the lower the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the concrete will be Bai, (2020), Wang, & Han, (2018), Chen, & Liu, (2016). Onésippe, Passe-Coutrin, & Toro, (2010) mixed bagasse fibers with different mass fractions and different

treatments into concrete, studied the change of its thermal conductivity and obtained the relationship between the fiber content and fiber treatment on the thermal conductivity of concrete as shown in Figure 4 (CBAGP in the figure).

Denotes heat-treated bagasse fiber-reinforced concrete specimens, and CBAGB denotes alkali-treated bagasse fiber-reinforced concrete specimens).

As can be seen in Fig. 4, the thermal conductivity of the specimens decreased significantly after incorporating bagasse fibers, especially when the mass fraction of the incorporated fibers reached 3%, the thermal conductivity of specimens CBAGP and CBAGB both decreased to In addition, it can be seen from Fig. 4 that the different treatments of the fibers also have a significant effect on the thermal insulation enhancement. In addition, it can also be seen from Fig. 4 that different treatments of fibers also have significant effects on the enhancement of thermal insulation performance, and heat-treated bagasse fibers have better thermal insulation enhancement than alkali-treated bagasse fibers, which is mainly due to the lower cellulose content of heat-treated bagasse fibers, while alkali-treated bagasse fibers have more decomposition of hemicellulose and lignin, which leads to the elevation of their cellulose content.

In addition, the crop straw fiber in the magnesium chloride cement matrix made of blocks, the thermal conductivity can even be reduced to 0.15 W / (m·K), about one-tenth of the thermal conductivity of ordinary concrete (Kang, 2014), greatly improving the thermal insulation performance of the material. Researchers will also be straw fiber blended into the mortar made of thermal insulation mortar (Feng, 2016; Ni, et al., 2014), thus expanding the application of plant fibers.

Other Properties of Plant Fiber-Reinforced Concrete

Durability

The durability of concrete includes frost resistance, resistance to chloride infiltration, etc. Researchers have also carried out a lot of studies on the effect of plant fibers on the durability of concrete.

Frost resistance refers to the property of the material in the water content situation, after many cycles of freezing and thawing without damage, and no significant decline in mechanical strength. After adding plant fibers to concrete, the fibers play the role of three-dimensional reinforcement, which not only increases the friction between cementitious materials but also prevents the expansion of cracks, effectively curbing the loss of quality of the composite material under the action of freezing and thawing cycles, thus improving the freezing resistance of the material (Yang, 2020). Researchers added fibers such as rice straw, coconut palm, and jute to concrete, all of which improved the frost resistance of concrete (Chen, et al., 2015; Gong, 2018).

Chloride ion erosion will destroy the passivation film on the surface of steel reinforcement in concrete, leading to accelerated corrosion of steel reinforcement, thus reducing the durability of reinforced concrete structures (Xu, et al., 2017). Plant fiber can improve the pore structure of concrete, prolong the path of chloride ion penetration, and prevent the development of internal cracks in concrete, therefore, the incorporation of plant fibers can improve the ability of concrete to resist chloride ion penetration, the study Wang, et al. (2018) shows that when the mass fraction of straw fibers incorporated is 0.1%, the concrete has a very good resistance to chloride ion penetration.

Endotrophic effect of plant fibers on concrete

With the cement hydration in the concrete produced by the solid products continuing to lap, the cement paste body internal formation of different sizes, interlocking capillary pores, and gradually destroys the pore water connectivity

(Jensen, & Hansen, 2001). When the water inside the cement paste is consumed by hydration, self-drying will occur inside the cement paste, causing self-shrinkage or even cracking (Wang, & Zhang, 2020). The unique cavity structure of plant fiber has good hydrophilicity, which can enhance the performance of concrete, but also can be used as the internal curing material of concrete, releasing the internal water in the late stage of cement hydration, providing the water needed for the hydration reaction of cement, avoiding the drying shrinkage and cracking of concrete (Guo, et al., 2020; Jian, et al., 2014; Zhang, 2015). The study shows that when the dosage of bamboo fibers in cement mortar reaches 2.0 kg / m³, compared with no dosage of bamboo fibers in cement mortar, the dosage of bamboo fibers in cement mortar is much higher than that of no dosage of bamboo fibers.

The cracking area of mortar with bamboo fibers was reduced by 69% (Liu, 2016), when the cement mortar was mixed with 0.3% by volume of flax fibers, it could make the cement sand

The total crack area of the slurry was reduced by 99.5% and the maximum crack width was reduced by 98.5% (Xu, 2013).

Conclusion

1) Plant fiber has the advantages of lightweight, high specific strength, large elongation at break, etc. It can replace man-made fibers to enhance the performance of concrete, and improve the high brittleness of concrete, and through the modification of plant fibers on the concrete enhancement effect is better, the concrete has better stability and durability.

2) Plant fiber enhancement of concrete mechanical properties of different characteristics: enhance the tensile strength of concrete, the use of the long fiber laying method can achieve the best enhancement effect, but the short fiber mixing method has a wider range of applications; to enhance the compressive strength of concrete, fiber length, fiber mixing, water-cement ratio, and other factors will affect the enhancement effect; to enhance the impact performance of concrete, the effect of its

enhancement and the impact resistance of concrete, with a wide range of correlations. Plant fiber dosage in a wide range of positive correlations.

3) Sugar substances in plant fibers can slow down the hydration of cement, plant fibers used in mass concrete construction, not only reduce the cement hydration process of the peak temperature of the concrete core area but also can make the temperature peak backward, thus effectively reducing the temperature difference between inside and outside of the mass concrete and improve the cracking resistance of mass concrete.

4) Plant fiber blended into concrete can enhance the thermal insulation performance and durability of concrete, and through the fiber on the concrete within the conservation effect, can reduce the cracking of concrete, to overcome the shortcomings of the concrete is easy to crack, expand the scope of application of concrete.

5) Although many studies have shown that plant fibers have a good enhancement effect on various properties of concrete and can make up for the many deficiencies of concrete, however, due to the differences in test conditions, the conclusions reached by many researchers are not entirely consistent. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct more in-depth research on the role of plant fiber-enhanced concrete according to the various working conditions in actual engineering applications, to achieve the best enhancement effect.

References

- Al-Oraimi, S. K., & Seibi, A. C. (1995). Mechanical characterisation and impact behaviour of concrete reinforced with natural fibres. *Composite Structures*, 32(1-4), 165-171. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-8223\(95\)00038-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-8223(95)00038-0)
- Azzmi, N. M., & Yatim, J. M. (2018). Kenaf fibrous concrete: Mechanical properties with different fiber volume fractions. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, 8(4), 1036. <https://doi.org/10.18517/ijaseit.8.4.5369>
- Bai, S. Q. (2020). Study on properties of plant fiber concrete. *New Technology & New Products of China*, 24, 73-75. (in Chinese).
- Barra, B. N., Santos, S. F., Bergo, P. V. A., et al. (2015). Residual sisal fibers treated by methane cold plasma discharge for potential application in cement-based material. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 77, 691-702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.09.016>
- Bonnet-Masimbert, P. A., Gauvin, F., Brouwers, H. J. H., et al. (2020). Study of modifications on the chemical and mechanical compatibility between cement matrix and oil palm fibers. *Results in Engineering*, 7, 100150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2020.100150>
- Chakraborty, S., Kundu, S. P., & Roy, A. (2013). Effect of jute as fiber reinforcement controlling the hydration characteristics of cement matrix. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 52(3), 1252-1260. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie3008453>
- Chen, B., & Liu, N. (2016). Experimental investigation on green concrete using magnesium phosphate cement (MPC) and rape stalk. *Journal of Building Materials*, 19(6), 1046-1050. (in Chinese).
- Chen, X., Liu, G., Wang, X., et al. (2018). Research progress of sisal fiber reinforced cementitious composites. *Silicate Bulletin*, 37(11), 3481-3486+3491.
- Chen, Y., Liang, Y. Z., Liu, D. X., et al. (2015). Plant fiber reinforced effects on resistance durability of vegetation-growing concrete frost. *Hubei Agricultural Sciences*, 54(19), 4840-4844. (in Chinese).
- Claramunt, J., Ardanuy, M., García-Hortal, J. A., et al. (2011). The hornification of vegetable fibers to improve the durability of cement mortar composites. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 33(5), 586-595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2011.03.003>
- Çomak, B., Bideci, A., & Salli Bideci, Ö. (2018). Effects of hemp fibers on characteristics of cement-based mortar. *Construction and Building*

Materials, 169, 794-799.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.03.013>

De Andrade Silva, F., Mobasher, B., & Filho, R. D. T. (2009). Cracking mechanisms in durable sisal fiber reinforced cement composites. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 31(10), 721-730.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2009.07.002>

De Klerk, M., Kayondo, M., Moelich, G., et al. (2020). Durability of chemically modified sisal fiber in cement-based composites. *Construction and Building Materials*, 241, 117835.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.11.7835>

Dos Santos, C., Cardoso, F. G., Da Silva, J. R., et al. (2022). Modification of short sugarcane bagasse fibers for application in cementitious composites: A statistical approach to mechanical and physical properties. *Construction and Building Materials*, 353, 129072.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.12.9072>

Farooqi, M. U., & Ali, M. (2019). Effect of pre-treatment and content of wheat straw on energy absorption capability of concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 224, 572-583.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.07.092>

Feng, L. Z. (2016). Study on preparation and performance research of wheat straw-MOC composite insulation mortar (Master's thesis, Shandong Agricultural University). (in Chinese).

Feng, X., Zuo, T., Sun, N., et al. (2022). Greenhouse gas emission reduction effect of centralized heating project with straw molding fuel. *Chinese Journal of Ecological Agriculture*, 30(4), 702-712.

Ferreira, S. R., De Andrade Silva, F., Lima, P. R. L., et al. (2017). Effect of hornification on the structure, tensile behavior and fiber matrix bond of sisal, jute and curau fiber cement-based composite systems. *Construction and Building Materials*, 139, 551-561.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.02.069>

Ferreira, S. R., De Andrade Silva, F., Lima, P. R. L., et al. (2015). Effect of fiber treatments on the sisal fiber properties and fiber-matrix bond in cement-based systems. *Construction and Building Materials*, 101, 730-740.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.10.028>

Filho, J. A. M., Silva, F. A., & Filho, R. D. T. (2013). Degradation kinetics and aging mechanisms on sisal fiber cement composite systems. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 40, 30-39.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2013.04.002>

Gong, M., Pan, A., Zhang, Z., et al. (2023). Study on the pull-out behavior of steel fibers in ultra-high performance fiber-reinforced concrete. *Silicate Bulletin*, 42(8), 2764-2772.

Gong, Y. Q. (2018). Experimental study on performance of jute fiber high strength concrete (Master's thesis, University of Science and Technology Liaoning). (in Chinese).

Guo, A. F., Sun, Z. H., & Satyavolu, J. (2020). Impact of modified kenaf fibers on shrinkage and cracking of cement pastes. *Construction and Building Materials*, 264, 120230.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.12.0230>

Guo, Y., Li, L., Yang, C., et al. (2022). Research progress of plant fiber reinforced concrete. *Silicate Bulletin*, 41(10), 3347-3358.

Gupta, M., & Kumar, M. (2019). Effect of nano silica and coir fiber on compressive strength and abrasion resistance of concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 226, 44-50.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.07.201>

Hwang, C. L., Tran, V. A., Hong, J. W., et al. (2016). Effects of short coconut fiber on the mechanical properties, plastic cracking behavior, and impact resistance of cementitious composites. *Construction and Building Materials*, 127, 984-992.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.10.026>

- Islam, M. S., & Ahmed, S. J. (2018). Influence of jute fiber on concrete properties. *Construction and Building Materials*, 189, 768-776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.09.058>
- Jensen, O. M., & Hansen, P. F. (2001). Autogenous deformation and RH-change in perspective. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 31(12), 1859-1865. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846\(01\)00608-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846(01)00608-6)
- Jia, W., & Li, L. (2023). Mechanical properties of dry and water-saturated basalt fiber concrete under different strain rates. *Journal of Changjiang Academy of Sciences*, 40(8), 170-176.
- Jian, S. W., Wang, T., Ma, B. G., et al. (2014). Study on the effect of the modified rice straw on the performance of the cement-based materials. *Materials Review*, 28(6), 132-135. (in Chinese).
- Jiang, P., Fang, J., Pang, J., et al. (2020). Mechanical and microscopic property analysis of plant fiber shotcrete. *Journal of Changjiang Academy of Sciences*, 37(8), 137-141+149.
- Kang, Y. (2014). Study on using straw resources developing rural building wall products (Master's thesis, Lanzhou University of Technology). (in Chinese).
- Lam, T. F., & Bin Mohamad Yatim, J. (2015). Mechanical properties of kenaf fiber reinforced concrete with different fiber content and fiber length. *Journal of Asian Concrete Federation*, 1(1), 11-21.
- Lee, S. G., Choi, S. S., Park, W. H., et al. (2003). Characterization of surface modified flax fibers and their biocomposites with PHB. *Macromolecular Symposia*, 197(1), 89-100. <https://doi.org/10.1002/masy.200351209>
- Li, C. F., Su, Y. W., Chen, G. P., et al. (2013). Study on properties of straw fiber reinforced concrete. *Concrete*, 10, 30-32, 37. (in Chinese).
- Li, M., Pu, Y. Q., Thomas, V. M., et al. (2020). Recent advancements of plant-based natural fiber-reinforced composites and their applications. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 200, 108254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.108254>
- Li, X., Tabil, L. G., & Panigrahi, S. (2007). Chemical treatments of natural fiber for use in natural fiber-reinforced composites: A review. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 15(1), 25-33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-006-0042-3>
- Liu, L. F., Yu, J. Y., Cheng, L. D., et al. (2009). Mechanical properties of poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) biocomposites reinforced with surface modified jute fiber. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 40(5), 669-674. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.02.004>
- Liu, Q. L., Liu, B. H., & Zhang, Q. (2012). Research on mechanical properties of cole straw fiber reinforced concrete. *China Concrete and Cement Products*, 12, 51-53. (in Chinese).
- Liu, Y. Y. (2016). Performance research of mortar reinforced with bamboo fiber (Master's thesis, Central South University of Forestry & Technology). (in Chinese).
- Ma, H. Y., Yue, C. J., Yu, H. F., et al. (2020). Experimental study and numerical simulation of impact compression mechanical properties of high-strength coral aggregate seawater concrete. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 137, 103466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2019.103466>
- Madhwani, H., Sathyan, D., & Mini, K. M. (2021). Study on durability and hardened state properties of sugarcane bagasse fiber reinforced foam concrete. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46, 4782-4787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.04.396>
- Munawar, S. S., Umemura, K., & Kawai, S. (2007). Characterization of the morphological, physical, and mechanical properties of seven nonwood plant fiber bundles. *Journal of Wood Science*, 53(2), 108-113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10086-006-0838-8>
- Naraganti, S. R., Pannem, R. M. R., & Putta, J. (2019). Impact resistance of hybrid fibre

reinforced concrete containing sisal fibres. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 10(2), 297-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2019.01.005>

Ni, Y., Sun, L. Z., & Wu, Q., et al. (2014). Study on property test of thermal insulation mortar mixed with plant fiber. *New Building Materials*, 41(7), 82-86. (in Chinese).

Niu, H., Gao, J., Li, G., et al. (2023). Study on flexural performance of high-strength recycled concrete beams with polyvinyl alcohol fiber. *Experimental Mechanics*, 38(5), 634-644.

Onésippe, C., Passe-Coutrin, N., & Toro, F. (2010). Sugar cane bagasse fibres reinforced cement composites: Thermal considerations. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 41(4), 549-556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.01.011>

Onuaguluchi, O., & Banthia, N. (2016). Plant-based natural fiber reinforced cement composites: A review. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 68, 96-108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2016.02.014>

Ramakrishna, G., & Sundararajan, T. (2005). Impact strength of a few natural fibre reinforced cement mortar slabs: A comparative study. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 27(5), 547-553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2004.09.006>

Ribeiro, B., Yamamoto, T., & Yamashiki, Y. (2020). A study on the reduction in hydration heat and thermal strain of concrete with addition of sugarcane bagasse fiber. *Materials*, 13(13), 3005. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13133005>

Sawsen, C., Fouzia, K., Mohamed, B., et al. (2015). Effect of flax fibers treatments on the rheological and the mechanical behavior of a cement composite. *Construction and Building Materials*, 79, 229-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.01.035>

Sellami, A., Merzoud, M., & Amziane, S. (2013). Improvement of mechanical properties of green concrete by treatment of the vegetal fibers. *Construction and Building Materials*, 47, 1117-

1124.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.04.018>

Shang, J., Zhao, T. J., Wang, L. Q., et al. (2019). Research on direct tensile experiments of high ductile vegetable fiber reinforced cementitious composites. *Bulletin of the Chinese Ceramic Society*, 38(1), 218-223, 230. (in Chinese).

Sun, D. (2016). Surface modification of natural fibers using plasma treatment: Biodegradable green composites. In John Wiley & Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119289746>

Talavera-Pech, W. A., Montiel-Rodríguez, D., Paat-Estrella, J. D. L. A., et al. (2021). Improvement in the carbonation resistance of construction mortar with cane bagasse fiber added. *Materials*, 14(8), 2066. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14082066>

Wang, G. H., & Han, Y. (2018). Research on the performance of straw fiber concrete. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 394, 032080. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/394/3/032080>

Wang, J. B., Ren, H. C., & Zhang, T., et al. (2018). Study on resistance to chloride ion penetration of wheat straw fiber concrete. *New Building Materials*, 45(11), 131-133 + 138. (in Chinese).

Wang, L. C., & Zhang, L. (2020). Research progress on concrete internal curing technology. *Journal of Building Materials*, 23(6), 1471-1478. (in Chinese).

Wei, J. Q., & Meyer, C. (2015). Degradation mechanisms of natural fiber in the matrix of cement composites. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 73, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2015.02.019>

Wen, C. C., Zhang, P., Wang, J., et al. (2022). Influence of fibers on the mechanical properties and durability of ultra-high-performance concrete: A review. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 52, 104370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2022.104370>

Xie, X. L. (2016). Preparation of cement-based composites reinforced with plant fiber and their

mechanical properties (Doctoral dissertation, Southwest Jiaotong University). (in Chinese).

Xu, L. (2013). Study of use of flax fibres to reduce the plastic shrinkage cracking in concrete. *Concrete*, 10, 91-94. (in Chinese).

Xu, P., Zhang, Y., & Jing, J., et al. (2017). Summary of research on concrete eroded by chloride ions. *Concrete*, 9, 45-48. (in Chinese).

Yan, L. B., Kasal, B., & Huang, L. (2016). A review of recent research on the use of cellulosic fibers, their fiber fabric reinforced cementitious, geo-polymer and polymer composites in civil engineering. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 92, 94-132.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.02.002>

Yang, G., Li, F., Zhang, Z., et al. (2023). Experimental study on dynamic fracture process of polyvinyl alcohol fiber concrete. *Silicate Bulletin*, 42(2), 454-462.

Yang, L. (2020). Research of modified straw cement-based materials (Master's thesis, Wuhan Polytechnic University). (in Chinese).

Yin, J., Ji, Y., Her, Z., et al. (2023). Research on mechanical properties of carbon fiber concrete. *Concrete*, (1), 64-67+72.

Zhang, H. Z., Hu, H., Zhang, D. F., et al. (2019). Experimental investigation on the mechanical properties of Artemisia annua fiber reinforced concrete. *Journal of Functional Materials*, 50(11), 11138-11143. (in Chinese).

Zhang, W. X. (2015). Durability, resistance to spalling after high temperature and creep characteristics of cellulose fibre reinforced concrete (Doctoral dissertation, Southeast University). (in Chinese).

Zhang, X. Y., Wang, D. D., Zhang, D. M., et al. (2019). Study on factors affecting mechanical properties of lightweight aggregate concrete mixed with straw fiber. *Bulletin of the Chinese Ceramic Society*, 38(5), 1369-1376. (in Chinese).

Zhang, Y. (2023). Experimental study on dynamic mechanical properties of basalt fiber concrete under impact loading. *Concrete*, (2), 25-29.

Zhou, C. H., Cai, L. P., Chen, Z. P., et al. (2020). Effect of kenaf fiber on mechanical properties of high-strength cement composites. *Construction and Building Materials*, 263, 121007.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.12.1007>

Appendix

Table 1. Mechanical Properties and Main Chemical Composition of Common Plant Fibers

Fiber type	Tensile Strength / MPa	Elastic modulus / GPa	Elongation at failure / %	Relative density (g-cm ⁻³)	Cellulose mass fraction / %	Hemi-cellulose mass fraction / %	Lignin mass fraction / %
Flax	343 ~ 2 000	27.6 ~ 103.0	1.2 ~ 3.3	1.4 ~ 1.5	72.5	14.5	2.5
Ramie	400 ~ 1 000	24.5 ~ 128.0	1.2 ~ 4.0	1.0 ~ 1.6	72.0	14.0	0.8
Hemp	270 ~ 900	23.5 ~ 90.0	1.0 ~ 3.5	1.4 ~ 1.5	81.0	20.0	4.0
Kenaf	223 ~ 930	14.5 ~ 53.0	1.5 ~ 2.7	1.4	53.5	21.0	17.0
Jute	320 ~ 800	30.0	1.0 ~ 1.8	1.3 ~ 1.5	67.0	16.0	9.0
Bamboo	140 ~ 800	11.0 ~ 32.0	2.5 ~ 3.7	0.6 ~ 1.1	34.5	20.5	26.0
Sisal	363 ~ 700	9.0 ~ 38.0	2.0 ~ 7.0	1.3 ~ 1.5	60.0	11.5	8.0
Pineapple	400 ~ 627	1.4	14.5	0.8 ~ 1.6	80.5	17.5	8.3
Bagasse	222 ~ 290	17.0 ~ 27.1	1.1	1.3	37.0	21.0	22.0
Coir	95 ~ 230	2.8 ~ 6.0	15.0 ~ 51.4	1.1 ~ 1.5	46.0	0.3	45.0

Source: Yan, Kasal, & Huang, 2016; Onuaguluchi, & Banthia, 2016; Wen, et al., 2022